

Personal Resiliency and School Engagement of Lifelong Learners in General Santos City

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Abstract:- This study aimed to identify the relationship between the personal resiliency and teachers' school engagement of the lifelong learners in General Santos City. This involved 68 randomly selected active solo parents' learners and 36 Alternative Learning System teachers. Questionnaires were used to identify personal resilience and the teachers' school engagement. This study applied a quantitative approach, and the data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). "Pearson r" correlation analysis was used to identify the relationship between personal resiliency and teachers' school engagement. The results of the study found that lifelong learners often have personal resiliency, and teachers also often have school engagement. In addition, the study found that three of the six components of teachers' school engagement showed significant influence on the personal resiliency of lifelong learners. The six components of teachers' school engagement are encouraging learning ownership, turning mistakes into opportunities, supplying a few go-to learning tools, allowing them to facilitate learning, finding time to play, and setting learning goals. Inferences from the study are deliberated, and supplementary research can be carried out to assess the short- and long-term impact of this study.

Keywords:- *Personal Resiliency, Teachers' School Engagement, Lifelong Learners.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Lifelong learning may be defined as a concept spanning an entire lifetime in the process of transforming experience into knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, emotions, beliefs, and the senses. It is not just continuing education; it is much more than that. Apparently, it is an important theoretical framework for the development of individuals' employability and flexibility. The inventive measurement of the lifelong learning concept lies in a new method of the development and situation of learning. Lifelong learning is important for the 21st century because of global demographics, environmental necessities, universal access to information due to new technologies, and the fast improvement in science and technology. They must have

developed skills that make them globally competitive individuals.

The Philippine government established the Alternative Learning System (ALS) to address the needs of the Filipino people who do not have a chance to go to formal education. It was established so that they could pursue their basic education. It is a government program to help Filipinos gain free basic education. Despite the privileges given by the government, there are still some learners who are not able to finish their education. Some of them have quit schooling for personal reasons. They still have some who have difficulties continuing their studies.

Many scholars and researchers have manifested that some school structures are not excellently effective in preparing students for the kinds of capabilities and skills that figure in the establishment of lifelong learning. New information and skills are essential for successful adaptation to a changing world and are constantly learned during life. Learners who have quit school may underachieve, leave school with insufficient training, and experience hardships in adulthood. Educators also need to be more innovative in their teaching strategies to help lifelong learners endure the lifelong learning process.

However, despite those various initiatives by the Philippine Government through the Department of Education, there are still some communities and people who need to cope with this rapidly changing society. It is from this vantage point that the researcher intends to go deeper into the study of the lifelong learning process.

II. PERSONAL RESILIENCE

Resilience, according to Hopler (2017), is a very important skill to learn because it empowers people to deal well with the stress, change, insecurity, and adversity that each person occasionally experiences. Those who are flexible can succeed in any situation. Resilience is being prepared, eager, and competent to fasten on to learning. It is being able to stick with difficulty and cope with feelings such as fear and frustration.

Despite all the benefits and good things about being a lifelong learner, some drivers and obstacles would increase or decrease motivation to engage in lifelong learning. This would test the resiliency of lifelong learners. Resilience is a way of acquiring a strong attitude when facing challenges and threatening events (Mowbray, 2016). He added that it is also about becoming stronger every time people overcome all the challenges that come along the way. Resilience is important for the success of a person; it is the ability needed for the growth of strong and flexible people. According to Price-Mitchell (2015), it empowers a person to develop from challenging experiences with a positive outlook on life. Hence, it will give people the emotional strength to handle pressure and adversity and be able to rebuild their lives after a calamity.

Resilience is the capacity to get up off the ground, brush yourself off, and keep moving on. It is also when you can handle stress and tough times in life. It is also the capacity to become strong, healthy, or successful again after something bad happens. Resilience is more reachable and available to some people than for others, but everyone can build up their resilience. In a growth mindset, people think that their most fundamental abilities can be improved through dedication and hard work; intelligence and ability are just the starting points. This view creates a love of learning and a resilience that is essential for great accomplishment.

There are four adult protective factors related to resilience. These can help individuals build on their strengths, such as creativity and setting limits, so they can better cope with the adversities and stresses of life. These are relationships, internal beliefs, initiative, and self-control. A relationship, according to Mackrain (2013), is a mutual, long-lasting, back-and-forth bond between a person and another person. The worth of relationships with other people influences the emotional resilience that a person can have in the face of an emotional or physical crisis. When learners have opportunities to connect with teachers who approach these relationships with a genuine desire to know them personally, they can make a peculiar contribution to their emerging adaptive capacity, self-sufficiency, resiliency, confidence, and knowledge of themselves. In terms of internal beliefs, Ghani (2015) stressed that beliefs signify a person's outlook about events and facilitate the initiating events of emotions and behaviors. He added that the encouraging significance of reactions and behaviors is habitually connected with beliefs. Initiative, as stated by Mackrain (2013), is the ability to make optimistic choices and decisions and act upon them. An initiative is the start of something with the hope that it will continue. A person with initiative is encouraged to do things. If the person takes the initiative, they are willing to get things done on their own. And lastly, according to Mackrain (2013), self-control is the ability to experience a variety of feelings and express them using the words and actions people consider applicable.

➤ *School Engagement*

Teachers wanted their learners to become successful in their endeavors. They want their learners to become teachers and leaders too. They make sure that their learners continue learning and growing. They also have accountability to deliver an innovative level of training that is applicable, operative, and socially appealing for learners (William, 2017). Teachers must recognize their students' likes, dislikes, interests, or preferred results to see if they can include any of those in their lesson in a way that the learners participate with the content. They must not persuade or force them to be excited about something. Teachers should know how their learners learn and establish learning environments that build independent relationships and promote a strong culture of learning. They should promote learners' sense of ownership and responsibility for their own learning. Learning ownership, according to McClaskey (2018), means that learners are driven, involved, and self-directed. She added that learners can monitor their own improvement, reveal their learning based on mastery of content, and understand how they learn.

Meanwhile, educators also allow learners to learn from their mistakes. Teachers must treat errors, according to Watanabe-Crockett (2019), as learning opportunities and not wrongdoing. Lessons from mistakes can show better ways to think and work and will let the learners grow mentally and emotionally. Teachers have different tricks that help their learners learn. According to Watanabe-Crockett (2019), there are numerous ways for teachers to better assist their students. Every learner has their own way of sharing their knowledge and ideas, so teachers must give them opportunities to do what they can do. McIntosh (2011) pointed out in his blog that if the teachers let their learners follow their personal ideas, they make up at least a third of the intended activity, and it becomes their most unforgettable and happy experience at school. He added that it is significant for the students not to attempt to resolve the problem but simply examine it and understand it from different viewpoints. According to Watanabe-Crockett (2019), the learners can impart valuable teachings of learning proprietorship and involvement to others, and they can inspire their co-learners. He added that the learning retention of learners would be maximized when they taught their knowledge to someone else. Play, according to Mead (2019), is essentially important to learning, and it helps enhance learning and develop basic skills such as inquiry, expression, research, and collaboration. It can pull together the reasonable and innovative parts of the brain. The learners will learn by matching physical experiences with communications with other people and their personal feelings. She added that play gives learners a chance to practice what they have learned. According to Watanabe-Crockett (2019), setting learning goals means securing that learning should have a purpose, which means that learners will have an end output in mind. Teachers must let their learners have an effective and meaningful motivation for learning. The teachers are accountable for creating lessons that will empower the learners to cultivate literacy skills and awareness.

The educational system's willingness to collaborate with its learners is significant for various forms of learning achievement. An institution must support both educators and learners to improve their abilities in gathering the right information because learners must be able to critically assess the sources of information. A school also needs to have a close connection with the local community, as pointed out by Bryce et al. (2000), developing what has been defined as a unified network of connections. School engagement, according to Fredricks (2016), is perceived as a solution to such signs of learner isolation. He added that it might protect learners from stopping schooling. Educators may consider different aspects of students' learning. They may improve their quality of teaching, which would stimulate the learners' involvement and participation. Learners were more engaged if teachers met their needs for relatedness and if they felt a sense of belongingness and were recognized, appreciated, involved, and stimulated by others.

III. METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach since it included numerical and quantifiable data in a systematic way of investigating phenomena and their relationships (Leedy, 1993). This is also a correlational study as it attempts to determine the existence and degree of association between teachers' school engagement for lifelong learners as the independent variable and the personal resiliency of learners as independent variables.

The respondents' selection process was based on the purposive sampling method. This study involved 68 randomly selected active solo parents' learners and 36 ALS teachers from fifteen (15) districts of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in General Santos City.

The instrument used in this study was the questionnaire because of its effectiveness and practicality. The instrument consists of two parts. Part I of the instrument was adopted and modified by the researcher from the Devereux Adult Resilience Survey (DARS) by Mackrain (2013), which determined the

personal resiliency of the lifelong learners. Part II of the questionnaire, adopted and modified from Watanabe-Crockett (2019), determined the approaches to school engagement to build lifelong learning skills in the learners and the validity of the questionnaire obtained from the three experts in the field.

➤ *Subject of the Study*

The respondents were lifelong learners and teachers from fifteen (15) districts of the Alternative Learning System (ALS) in General Santos City. Sixty-eight (68) active solo parents' lifelong learners answered Part I of the questionnaire, and thirty-six (36) ALS teachers answered Part II of the questionnaire.

➤ *Research Instrument*

The researcher determined the personal resiliency and school engagement of the lifelong learners in General Santos City. The instrument used was the questionnaire because of its effectiveness and practicality. The instrument consists of two parts. Part I of the instrument was adopted and modified by the researcher from the Devereux Adult Resilience Survey (DARS) by Mackrain (2013), which determined the personal resiliency of the lifelong learners. Part II of the questionnaire, adopted and modified from Watanabe-Crockett (2019), determined the approaches to school engagement to build lifelong learning skills in the learners and the validity of the questionnaire obtained from the three experts in the field, comprising two professors from Mindanao State University Graduate School and the Alternative Learning System Program Specialist.

➤ *Statistical Treatment*

The researcher used weighted means in analyzing and interpreting the data gathered. To determine personal resiliency and school engagement for lifelong learners, a five-point Likert scale was used. To determine the significant association between the personal resiliency and school engagement of the lifelong learners, data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and "Pearson r" correlation analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ *Level of Protective Factors on Personal Resiliency of the Lifelong Learners*

Table 1a. Personal Resiliency of Lifelong Learners in terms of Relationship

Relationship	Mean	Description
1. I have good friends who support me.	3.72	Often
2. I have a mentor or someone who shows me the way.	4.13	Often
3. I provide support to others.	3.58	Often
4. I am empathetic to others.	3.58	Often
5. I trust my close friends.	3.58	Often
Mean	3.72	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

Lifelong learners, as evaluated in terms of relationships, are rated **often** with a mean of (M = 3.72). This means that they have good friends and likewise have mentors who show them the way, rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.13). It can be gleaned that lifelong learners provide support, are empathetic to others, and trust their close friends, as rated **often** with a mean of (M = 3.58). This finding conforms with the study of Mackrain (2013), which noted that the quality of relationships with other people influences how emotionally resilient a person can be in the face of an emotional or physical crisis. More quality social support from family and friends can really help you be more flexible and resilient in stressful situations. In addition to resiliency, it is important to have the ability to create and maintain enduring friendships and love. Similarly, this also supports the statement of Kizildag et al. (2017) that school is not only an educational place but also a place where they can mingle with their friends, which helps them improve their school enthusiasm.

Table 1b. Personal Resiliency of Lifelong Learners in terms of Internal Beliefs

Internal Beliefs	Mean	Descriptive
1. My role as a mother is important.	4.70	Always
2. I have personal strengths.	4.47	Often
3. I am creative.	4.08	Often
4. I have strong beliefs.	4.32	Often
5. I am hopeful about my future.	4.60	Always
Mean	4.43	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of internal beliefs, solo parents believe that their role as mothers is important, and it is rated as **always** with a mean of (M = 4.70), and they are hopeful about their future, rated as **always** with a mean of (M = 4.60). Solo parents have personal strengths rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.47) and strong beliefs (M = 4.32). They are also creative, which was rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.08). The result of these findings is in conformity with the study by Ghani et al. (2015), which found that the belief system of single mothers is positive while their emotional well-being is moderate.

Table 1c. Personal Resiliency of Lifelong Learners in terms of Initiative

Initiative	Mean	Description
1. I communicate effectively with those around me.	3.91	Often
2. I try many different ways to solve a problem.	4.08	Often
3. I have a hobby that I engage in.	3.82	Often
4. I seek out new knowledge and I am open to new ideas.	3.67	Often
5. I can ask for help.	3.91	Often
Mean	3.88	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of initiative, lifelong learners tried many different ways to solve a problem, which was rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.08). They communicate effectively with those around them and ask for help rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 3.91). They also have a hobby that they are engaged in that is rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 3.82) and seek out new knowledge and are open to new ideas, rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 3.67). This means that the result of these findings is supported by Frese and Fay (2001), who show initiative by spotting and acting on opportunities that their colleagues or leaders have not observed. They are interested in their organization and how it works, and they keep their minds open to new ideas and new possibilities.

Table 1d. Personal Resiliency of Lifelong Learners in terms of Self-Control

Self-Control	Mean	Description
1. I express my emotions.	4.01	Often
2. I set limits for myself.	3.91	Often
3. I am flexible.	4.02	Often
4. I can calm myself down.	4.00	Often
5. I am able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear and anger.	3.88	Often
Mean	3.96	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of self-control, solo parents are flexible, and this was rated as **often** with a mean of ($M = 4.02$), and they express their emotions rated as **often** with a mean of ($M = 4.01$). They **often** also calm themselves down with a mean of ($M = 4.00$) and set limits for themselves with a mean of ($M = 3.91$). They are able to handle unpleasant or painful feelings like sadness, fear, and anger, which were rated as **often** with a mean of ($M = 3.88$).

These findings are regarded with the self-control cited by Pronk & Kokkoris (2018), which represents the ability to prevail over attractive desires for the sake of long-term goals. They added that it gives emphasis to the ability to hold in goal-directed behaviors and successful goal progress, which are often mentioned among the most essential benefits of high self-control. Moreover, high levels of self-control are connected with less and stronger dependence on established daily routines and a beneficial lifestyle.

➤ *Approaches of School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills in the Learners*

Table 2a. Teachers' School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills of Learners in terms of Encouraging Learning Ownership

Encouraging Learning Ownership	Mean	Description
1. I make my learners feel that they are responsible for their own learning.	4.69	Always
2. I encourage them to actively participate in the classroom.	4.94	Always
3. I give homework to my learners.	3.61	Often
4. I ask the opinions of my learners.	4.58	Always
5. I allow my learners to work independently.	4.55	Always
Mean	4.47	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

The teachers evaluated that in terms of encouraging learning ownership, they make their learners feel that they are responsible for their own learning, with a mean of ($M = 4.69$) and encourage them to actively participate in the classroom, with a mean of ($M = 4.94$) both are described as **always**. The teachers give homework to their learners, described as often with a mean of ($M = 3.61$), and ask the opinion of the learners, rated as **always** with a mean of ($M = 4.58$). In addition, the teachers allow their learners to work independently, described as **always** with a mean of ($M = 4.55$).

Educators encourage learning ownership. Similarly, this agrees with the study of William (2017), which stated that this gives learners the freedom to learn on their own, which can boost their self-esteem. This means that learners do encourage developing an ability to help others; hence, they can also develop insightful interdependence by intermingling with their peers and communicating with a variety of people.

Table 2b. Teachers' School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills of Learners in terms of Turning Mistakes into Opportunities

Turning Mistakes into Opportunities	Mean	Description
1. I allow my learners to learn from their own mistakes.	4.47	Often
2. I allow them to try new things.	4.44	Often
3. I show them better ways to think and work.	4.50	Always
4. I provide them insights into hidden knowledge and awareness.	4.27	Often
5. I treat their mistakes as opportunities and never as crimes.	4.25	Often
Mean	4.38	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of turning mistakes into opportunities, the teachers show better ways to think and work, described as **always** with a mean of ($M = 4.50$), and allow them to learn from their own mistakes, rated as **often** with a mean of ($M = 4.47$). They also often allow their learners to try new things with a mean of ($M = 4.44$) and provide them insights into hidden knowledge and awareness with a mean of ($M = 4.27$). Teachers treat their mistakes as opportunities and never as crimes, rated as **often** with a mean of ($M = 4.25$). This finding is consistent with the study by Watanabe (2019), which found that teachers must treat errors as learning opportunities and not misconduct. Lessons from mistakes can show better ways to think and work and will let the learners grow mentally and emotionally.

Table 2c. Teachers' School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills of Learners in terms of Supplying a Few Go-To Learning Tools

Supplying a Few Go-To Learning Tools	Mean	Description
1. I give tricks that help my learners.	4.16	Often
2. I allow them to do what they want to do.	3.86	Often
3. I support them with their ideas.	4.33	Often
4. I use new learning tools.	4.44	Often
5. I give them opportunities to do things that they can.	4.47	Often
Mean	4.25	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of supplying a few go-to learning tools, teachers give opportunities to their learners to do things that they can, described as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.47) and use new learning tools (M = 4.44). Teachers support their learners with their ideas, rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.33), and give tricks that can help their learners (M = 4.16). They also allow their learners to do what they want to do; it was described as **often**, with a mean of (M = 3.86). This means that teachers utilize various strategies to let their learners respond to the learning process. This finding is consistent with the study of Jackson (2016), which found that to help in developing lifelong learners, increasing their achievement, and improving their school involvement, it was necessary that the school have realistic, project-based, and hands-on learning opportunities.

Table 2d. Teachers' School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills of Learners in terms of Allowing them to Facilitate Learning

Allowing them to Facilitate Learning	Mean	Description
1. I have group work in my class.	4.11	Often
2. I allow them to assist and guide others.	4.36	Often
3. I allow them to share their experiences in life.	4.77	Always
4. I challenge my learners.	4.47	Often
5. I allow them to show what they have.	4.27	Often
Mean	4.40	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of allowing the learners to facilitate learning, the teachers allow their learners to share their experiences in life described as **always** with a mean of (M = 4.77) and challenge their learners rated as **often** with a mean of (M = 4.47). They also allowed them to assist and guide others (M = 4.36) and allowed them to show what they have (M = 4.27) described as **often**. Moreover, they have group work in class described as often with a mean of (M = 4.11). The result of this study supported the study of Watanabe-Crockett (2019), which showed that learners can impart valuable teachings of learning proprietorship and involvement to others and inspire their co-learners. This means that learners will be more responsive if they are allowed to take the teaching reins.

Table 2e. Teachers' School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills of Learners in terms of Finding Time to Play

Finding Time to Play	Mean	Description
1. I allow them to act as an actor.	4.16	Often
2. I try to have role-playing in class.	4.02	Often
3. I let my learners characterize something.	4.00	Often
4. I let them perform in a theater.	3.11	Sometimes
5. I let them learn from themselves and from the others.	4.25	Often
Mean	3.91	Often

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of finding time to play, teachers let their learners learn from themselves and from the others (M = 4.25) and allow them to act as actors (M = 4.16). They also tried to have role-playing in class (M = 4.02) and let their learners to characterize something (M = 4.00) rated as **often**. In addition, they let their learners perform in a theater (M = 3.11) described as **sometimes**. This finding is consistent with the statement of Mead (2019) that through play the learners will learn by matching physical experiences. This means that through constant communication they will be able to relate their personal feelings. They will be able to express themselves.

Table 2f. Teachers' School Engagement to Build Lifelong Learning Skills of Learners in terms of Setting Learning Goals

Setting Learning Goals	Mean	Description
1. I give valid and worthwhile reasons for learning.	4.63	Always
2. I give my learners a meaningful and useful experience.	4.66	Always
3. I let them explain or visualize the performance goals that they wanted to achieve.	4.58	Always
4. I allow my learners to put together a simple plan to achieve a goal.	4.41	Often
5. I allow them to create their own achievable goals.	4.61	Always
Mean	4.58	Always

Legend: 4.50 - 5.00 – Always; 3.50 – 4.49 – Often; 2.50 – 3.49 – Sometimes; 1.50 – 2.49 – Rarely; 1.00 – 1.49 – Never

In terms of setting learning goals, the teachers give their learners meaningful and useful experiences ($M = 4.66$) and a valid and worthwhile reason for learning ($M = 4.63$). They also allow them to create their own achievable goals ($M = 4.61$) and let them explain or visualize the performance goals that they want to achieve ($M = 4.58$), and these two are rated as **always**. Moreover, they allow their learners to put together a simple plan to achieve a goal described as **often** with a mean of ($M = 4.41$). This is in conformity with the study of Watanabe-Crockett (2019), which shows that the teachers are accountable for creating lessons that will empower the learners to cultivate literacy skills and awareness.

Table 3. Relationship between Teachers' School Engagement and the Personal Resiliency of Lifelong Learners

Teachers' School Engagement	Personal Resiliency of Lifelong Learners		
	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	Remarks
Encourage learning ownership	0.432	0.000	with significant relationship
Turn mistakes into opportunities	0.137	0.451	no significant relationship
Supply a few go-to learning tools	0.337	0.000	with significant relationship
Allow them to Facilitate Learning	0.172	0.416	no significant relationship
Find time to play	0.198	0.370	no significant relationship
Set learning goals	0.323	0.000	with significant relationship

The result of the correlation showed that among the six components of teachers' school engagement, there are three that show significant influence on the personal resiliency of lifelong learners. These encourage learning ownership ($r = 0.432$, $p = 0.000$), supply a few go-to learning tools ($r = 0.337$, $p = 0.000$), and set learning goals ($r = 0.323$, $p = 0.000$).

This result indicates that learners tend to have higher personal resiliency when their teachers make them responsible for their learning, provide them with new learning tools, and give them worthwhile reasons for learning. The result supported the study of Deakin Crick et al. (2015), which found that the value of relationships and the social practices of classrooms and schools influenced students' engagement in the processes of learning. This means that the intellectual and emotional experience that students bring to the classroom reflects the personal and environmental characteristics of the learners, especially community and practice. The result also supported the study of Taylor & Parsons (2011) that learners want stronger relationships with their teachers and want them to institute learning environments that set up independent relationships and that promote and create a strong culture of learning. Open, caring, and respectful relationships between learners and teachers are essential to developing and supporting social and psychological engagement in learning. This is also in conformity with the study of Jackson (2016), which found that teachers have significant influence over the levels of engagement displayed by the learners in the classrooms, and

well-planned learning opportunities can increase learners' engagement and achievement.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The researcher concludes that the teachers' school engagement influences the personal resiliency of the lifelong learners. It helps the lifelong learners to stay connected in school despite the different situations that they have, especially the solo parents who have difficult times as they need to attend to the needs of their child or children. Teachers' encouragement of learning ownership makes lifelong learners feel that they are responsible for their own learning. In addition, they strive more for themselves and hope for a better future through Alternative Learning System education. Teachers' way of supplying a few go-to learning tools helps the learners be more active in school. They are more attentive if the teacher offers different teaching styles that make their schooling more fun and enjoyable. Moreover, in terms of setting learning goals by the teachers, it helps the lifelong learners to give worthwhile reasons for learning. This is the most important thing: they have goals for learning so that they are able to survive until the end and continue to hope for a better future.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following are hereby recommended: the collaboration of the national government and the different stakeholders should be continued in supporting lifelong learners. They should continue

advocating for the predicament of lifelong learners so that it gives them hope and courage to continue their studies despite the adversities that they have encountered in life. This is also to address issues and challenges encountered by the lifelong learners in a more planned and organized manner; in that way, it contributes towards enhancing the personal resiliency of the lifelong learners.

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